

GRADUATE'S EMPLOYABILITY: A TRACER STUDY FOR TEACHER EDUCATION GRADUATES

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ABSTRACT

As the landscape of education continually evolves to meet the demands of a dynamic society, it becomes imperative for teacher education institutions to assess the outcomes of their programs and the subsequent trajectories of their graduates. Thus, this study assessed the employability of the Bachelor in Elementary Education (BEED) and Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) graduates of the Arellano University, Jose Abad Santos Campus (AU-JAS Campus). The study employed descriptive design since its purpose is to obtain and present facts regarding demographic profile of the graduates. Purposive sampling was used in this study. The Arellano University tracer study questionnaire was used to gather data which consists of the following parts, General Information, Educational Background, Advance Trainings and Graduates Studies and Employment Information. Data were gathered from the Registration and Admission Office's list of education undergraduates from 2015-2019 who were then contacted to provide employment information via cellphone, emails and Facebook Messenger. There were 188 graduates traced; 68 or (36%) BEED and 120 or (64%) BSEd. The data were analyzed using frequency and percentage. One hundred twenty-two or 65% of BEED and BSEd graduates were personally applied to found a job after their graduation. One hundred twenty-three or (66%) were holding permanent/regular position. Ninety-two or 49% were employed within in private organization as they finished their degree. Majority (81%) or 153 of the teacher education graduates within the last 5 years found a job aligned to their specialization. The findings imply that AU teacher education graduates

are easily employed; teacher education is in demand nationally and internationally. The School of Education should recognize the paramount importance of staying attuned to the evolving needs of the education landscape and ensuring that its curriculum remains responsive and relevant. By leveraging the insights gained from a Five-Year Tracer Study, an Alumni Homecoming Program can be strategically designed to meet the evolving needs and interests of the alumni community, fostering sustained engagement and long-term success. Future studies may investigate the matching of competencies learned and their relevance in the workplace.

Keywords: *employment information, employability, teacher education graduates, tracer study*

INTRODUCTION

The knowledge and skills of the people run the nation's economy. Skills requirements change because of external investment, technological advancements, and globalization. People need to gain skills to be productive and earn a living to keep up with changes, and all of this may be accomplished through education. The employability of an academic institution's graduates is one of the elements that define its effectiveness. Graduate quality is very much a function of quality instruction and facilities because these will help ensure that graduates are equipped with the information, skills, and values necessary to work in their chosen fields. People go to universities and finish college degree with the goal of being employed and earn a living. The primary goal of Teacher Education institutes is to produce competent and highly trained graduates who can work both in the United States and overseas. They use several ways to achieve this important goal. They are always enhancing their curriculum content and delivery by hiring and retaining competent faculty members, developing instructional facilities, offering relevant student support systems, and cultivating a quality and excellence culture. According to Aclan (2018), it is the responsibility of HEIs to ensure that their graduates are employable.

The issue of higher education graduates' competencies has attracted people's attention and is widely discussed for the past decades by employers and academicians alike, in the Philippines and in international communities. Employers are said to have become more demanding of their prospective employees. Not only should they hold higher education credentials, but they also must possess certain competencies that will guarantee good job performance. Employers, aside from being demanding, also blame higher education institutions for not producing graduates without competencies. A civil engineer may have a credential in civil engineering, but does not possess other competencies which are equally important as his/her credential.

Competencies such as English, computer operation, communication skills, and team work have proven to be as equally important as the credentials. Employers who must spend extra money to train the graduates before they can work insist that higher education take responsibility of producing graduates that are not ready to work or fit into the work environment.

The demand of tertiary education is increasing because the people expect that with the expenditure they spend on higher education, they expect to get more in the return of investment. A successful career path, a good salary, and many others. In reality, however, a higher education diploma does not guarantee a good career, better employment or good income as competition in the labor market gets more severe with hundreds of thousands of higher education graduates go to the labor market competing for lesser jobs. In the studies of Cornillez (2021) and Clemencio (2019), salaries and benefits are the main reasons why most respondents continue in their jobs, and most respondents believe that their employment is related to the program they studied in university, and they find their newly acquired communication skills to be very valuable at work. This suggests that teacher education students should be constantly prepared with the required skills and information to contribute to graduates' success in taking the licensure examination, which leads to a stable and secure job.

In the study of Pardo (2020), the implementation of the country's K-12 Basic Education Program has presented a challenge to Teacher Education Institutions because the curriculum is required to be taught in new and unique methods. However, the emergence of the ASEAN Mutual Recognition Agreement (MRA) indicates a more competitive and deregulated educational system, with increased pressure on it to ensure that the next generations of workers are prepared for some amorphous job market of the twenty-first century. Future teachers should then be equipped for the professional world, entrepreneurship, and higher education to address the demands of the national and global communities. In addition to that, Mace (2012) emphasizes that the motive of the people's spending money in higher education is in an investment for future economic benefits and because it involves people's capital investment, accountability ought to take place. The people demand that higher education institutions be responsible for the money that they have invested.

According to Cuadra, LJ (2019), to align with the ASEAN higher education system, the institution must prioritize student mobility, credit transfers, quality assurance, and research clusters. Teacher Education Graduates highly acquired the employability skills such as problem solving, communication, planning and organizing from the university. Profile variable (sex) has no significant relationship to the employability skills acquisition of graduates (Ulanday, 2021).

Perhaps the most important objective of college education is employment. Most parents send their children to college with the hope that after graduation their children will be able to find a descent and stable job. This holds true to Filipino parents who took at the very value of college education as the most important legacy they can give their children and as the most effective means getting a job that would help build the future of their children. However, with the present quality of education and the pressing demands of the workforce industry, many parents and graduates get disappointed due to the inability of the graduates to get employed. This is partly because these graduates lack the necessary skills and qualifications required by the industry.

An ideal learning environment for a Teacher Education Institution is one in which its students acquire a high-quality education. Such learning environment achieves its vision, as shown by the quality of graduates who passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers. And this is also the yardstick for the quality teacher education program and performance of would-be teachers.

The University graduate tracer study gives useful information on what happens to our new graduates when they enter the workforce. It is also critical to determine how adequate the training supplied by our institution is in terms of overall success in their career life, as well as the level to which knowledge, communication, and other abilities have been developed. This tracer study can also give significant information for analyzing an institution's educational and training outcomes, and so serve as a foundation for future planning operations.

This tracer study is a follow up study to determine the employment status of Teacher Education Graduates of Arellano University, Jose Abad Santos Campus. It determines and assesses the status of Education students, present position, type of organization, employment status, occupational classification, number of years in the company and monthly income range. The findings of the study served as the basis in the preparation for the Alumni Home Coming Program.

Research Questions

The study intended to find out the status of the education graduates of Arellano University, Pasay City.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of Education Graduates in terms of Educational Background in the following years?
 - 1.1. 2019
 - 1.2. 2018
 - 1.3. 2017
 - 1.4. 2016
 - 1.5. 2015
2. What is the demographic profile of respondents in terms of employment information in the last five years?
3. Based on the Five-Year Tracer Study, what common findings will warrant a sustainable Alumni Home Coming Program?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive design since its purpose is to obtain and present facts regarding demographics of the graduates. Purposive sampling was used in this study. This is a non-probability type of sampling which chooses respondents who are

readily available (Polit & Beck, 2014). The respondents were the graduates of the School of Education from Batch 2015 to Batch 2019.

The Arellano University tracer study questionnaire was used to gather data which consists of the following parts, General Information, Educational Background, Advance Trainings and Graduates Studies and Employment Information. It was a ready-made survey questionnaire from the Alumni Services Department.

To facilitate the distribution and administration of the questionnaire, the researchers personally distributed and contacted the graduate's using cellphone or email addresses. Online questionnaires will also be made available through google forms and it will be forwarded to their active Facebook messenger account. The questionnaires can also be downloaded on MS Word format and can be send back through attachment.

RESULTS

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents as to Educational Background

Year of Graduation	BEEd	BSEd	Total	Percentage (%)
2019	12	19	31	16.49
2018	17	47	64	34.04
2017	16	26	42	22.34
2016	16	21	37	19.68
2015	7	7	14	7.45
Total	68	120	188	100

Table 2

Demographic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Employment Information

Employment Information	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
A. Acquiring Current Job		
Personally applied for the job	122	65.00
Arranged by school's job placement	19	10.00
Recommended by AU Faculty/Dean	43	23.00
Directly invited by the company.	4	2.00
Others	0	0.00
Total	188	100

B. Type of Organization		
Private	92	49.00
Public	89	47.00
NGO	7	4.00
Others	0	0.00
Total	188	100
C. Employment Status		
Regular/ Permanent	123	66.00
Casual	51	27.00
Part time	2	1.00
Contractual	12	6.00
Total	188	100
D. Occupational Classification		
Corporate Executive or Manager	0	0.00
Managing proprietor or Supervisor	3	2.00
Official of Government and Special Interest Organization	2	1.00
Educational	153	81.00
Laborer or Unskilled worker	0	0.00
Special Occupation	0	0.00
Trader or Related Worker	0	0.00
Market Sales Worker	22	12.00
Clerk	8	4.00
Technician or Associate Professional	0	0.00
Others	0	0.00
Total	188	100
E. Number of Years in the Company		
0-5	175	93.00
6-10	13	7.00
11-15	0	0.00
16-20	0	0.00
21-25	0	0.00
Total	188	100

F. Monthly Income Range		
Below 10, 000	15	8.00
10, 000-20, 000	151	80.00
21, 000-30, 000	20	11.00
31, 000 above	2	1.00
Total	188	100

DISCUSSION

The table 1 above shows that the most of the respondents were from batch 2018 with 64 or 34.04 percent. There were 14 or 7.45 percent respondents who graduated in 2015. It reveals that there is an increase of graduates from Batch 2015 to Batch 2018. There is a decrease of 48 percent of graduates during 2019 due to the implementation of K to 12 Curriculum.

Table 2 reveals the employment information of Education graduates. It can be seen from the table that majority of the respondents acquired their current job is personally applied for the job with 122 or 65 percent while 4 or 2% is directly invited by the company. Most of the respondents were belong to private organization with 92 Or 49 percent while 7 or 4 percent belongs to NGO's. In terms of employment status of the respondents, 123 or 66 percent were holding regular/permanent position while 2 or 1 percent enjoying their part time job. As far as occupational classification is concerned, 153 or 81 percent worked in the field of education while 2 or 1 percent employed as official of government and special interest organization. Almost 175 or 93 percent has 0-5 years in the company while 13 or 7 percent only acquired 6-10 years in the company. From the data, it can be gleaned that 151 or 80 percent of Education graduates is earning P10,000.00 to P20,000.00 while 2 or 1 percent has an initial gross of 31, 000 above of monthly earning.

It is consistent to the study of Cuadra, LJ (2019) to align with the ASEAN higher education system, the institution must prioritize student mobility, credit transfers, quality assurance, and research clusters. Teacher Education Graduates highly acquired the employability skills such as problem solving, communication, planning and organizing from the university. Profile variable (sex) has no significant relationship to the employability skills acquisition of graduates (Ulanday, 2021).

Conclusions

Based on the Five-Year Tracer Study, the common findings that will warrant a sustainable Alumni Home Coming Program, it revealed that most of the respondents were

currently employed, has a regular/permanent position in the private organization and employed in the field of education.

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Arellano University, School of Education provided quality education to the graduates as majority of them were employed.
2. The knowledge, skills, trainings, and curricular programs provided by the School of Education to its graduates were effective.
3. A Five-Year Tracer Study can provide valuable insights into the experiences and outcomes of graduates over an extended period. Identify alumni career trajectories, successes, and challenges. A sustainable Homecoming Program can incorporate events that cater to the professional development and networking needs of alumni based on their varied career paths. Determine where alumni are located geographically. If there are significant concentrations in specific regions, consider organizing regional events or ensuring that the main Homecoming event is accessible to alumni from diverse locations. Recognize any common challenges faced by alumni, such as job market trends, industry-specific issues, or personal development obstacles. Create program components that address these challenges and provide valuable support. Highlight significant milestones achieved by alumni, whether in their careers, personal lives, or contributions to society. This can add a celebratory dimension to the Homecoming Program and foster a sense of pride among the alumni community.

An Alumni Homecoming Program serves not only as a reunion but also as a platform for ongoing collaboration, mentorship, and support between alumni and the institution. By carefully planning and executing each component, the program can contribute to a lasting and positive relationship between the alma mater and its graduates.

Recommendations

1. The School of Education should recognize the paramount importance of staying attuned to the evolving needs of the education landscape and ensuring that its curriculum remains responsive and relevant. To achieve this, the school should commit to an annual practice of updating the status of its graduates and soliciting valuable feedback on potential curriculum enhancements. This iterative process aims to create a dynamic educational environment that fosters continuous improvement and aligns with the school's mission to produce educators who are well-prepared for the challenges of the modern educational landscape.
2. The School of Education faculty may encourage the students to be more motivated to work hard and persevere in whatever task and project assigned to them to develop their sense of responsibility and leadership.
3. Recognizing the dynamic nature of the education landscape and the need for educators to possess a diverse skill set, the School of Education should extend

beyond traditional classroom instruction, emphasizing the importance of exposure to various competitions, as well as specialized training and seminars.

4. The School of Education must continue to tap linkages that will bring possible employment opportunities for its graduates. Forge connections with educational associations, teacher unions, and other professional organizations that can provide insight into industry needs and facilitate networking opportunities.
5. Further tracer studies may include the assessment of competencies learned in the university and their relevance in the workplace. This will help improve the curriculum to be aligned with the industry needs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

I, Dr. Marlowe Louis F. Fabunan, thus declare that all information gathered and made available in this study was received with the consent of the respondents. They were appropriately informed and given the option to withdraw from the study at any time. The respondents' anonymity was maintained, they were not subjected to any form of harm, there was no conflict of interest in the study's conduct, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and the results were used purely for research.

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